

1 **Tailoring a glycerol-free cryopreservation protocol with anti-freeze**
2 **(glycol)proteins for commercial and native breeds of chicken**

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25 **ABSTRACT**

26 This study evaluated the effects of antifreeze proteins AFPI, AFPIII, and AFGP during
27 fresh processing, and freezing-thawing of chicken semen from a commercial broiler
28 breed (BB) and the local breed Yellow Hungarian (YH), using 0.6 mol/L DMA as
29 cryoprotectant. AFPI had small but significant ($p < 0.05$) positive effects on post-thaw
30 sperm viability and motility in BB. For YH semen, three freezing protocols with
31 different dilution rates (4×, 2.3×, 2.1×) were compared. Protocol 1 (dilution rate 4×)
32 gave the best post-thaw viability ($P < 0.001$) and was used further. Fertility rates (FR) of
33 pre-freezing steps were tested by inseminating WL hens (4 AI/hen in 2 weeks, $100 \times$
34 10^6 sp/dose). FRs for A) raw semen, B) chilled semen, C) B + DMA, D) B + AFPI,
35 and E) B + DMA + AFPI were 48.2, 3.7, 31.4, 21.4, and 16.1%, respectively. B was
36 lower than A ($p < 0.001$), while C–E were higher than B ($p < 0.005$). AFPI during freezing
37 gave no advantage compared with DMA, except for improved post-thaw DNA integrity.
38 Inseminations with frozen-thawed semen (8 AI/hen in 3 weeks, 100×10^6 sp/dose)
39 gave low FR with YH semen, regardless of hen type. FR with YH semen was 0%
40 without AFPI and 1.5% with AFPI. The oviduct embryo mortality ($18.0\% \pm 1.4$)
41 observed across all the different hen groups suggested insufficient number of
42 spermatozoa inseminated. In conclusion, AFPI improved some post-thaw traits, but
43 fertility outcomes remain inconclusive. Preventing pre-freezing fertility loss and
44 increasing sperm dose concentration are required.

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46 Key Words: fertility, DMA, AFPI, AFPIII, AFGP, chicken, rare breed, semen freezing.

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50 **1. Introduction**

51 Sperm cryopreservation plays an important role in ex-situ conservation of genetic
52 diversity. However, loss of cell functional intactness by ice formation is a major
53 obstacle in many livestock species. Currently, the dose of cryopreserved chicken semen
54 required for artificial insemination (AI) is 50 times higher than that of fresh semen [1]
55 and even with such high sperm dosage, the fertilization rates with frozen-thaw semen
56 remain variable and poor for many breeds/lines of chickens [1–4]. Moreover, the
57 demonstrated dependence between cryotolerance and chicken breed [5] seems to
58 indicate the need to adapt cryopreservation protocols to the breed of interest. Thus,
59 research continues evolving regarding chicken sperm cryopreservation.

60 The freezing of a tissue or a suspension of cells leads to cryoinjury and cell death.
61 Much of this is related to the formation of ice and the resulting osmotic stress [6].
62 Intracellular ice formation is considered absolutely lethal and can be prevented by
63 allowing extracellular ice formation at optimal cooling rates [3,6,7]. However, the large
64 extracellular ice masses and ice crystals can physically damage cells. This damage can
65 vary depending on the form and size of ice crystals which is affected, amongst other
66 factors, by recrystallization, i.e., the change in the size, shape or orientation of
67 individual crystals after the completion of solidification [8].

68 Antifreeze proteins (e.g. AFPI, AFPIII, AFGP) are found in freeze-avoiding and
69 freeze-tolerant organisms (animals, plants, fungi, or bacteria). These proteins are
70 capable to bind to the surface of nascent ice crystals [9,10] and control the size, shape
71 and aggregation of smaller ice crystals, thus affecting the mechanical stress and cell
72 damage caused by ice [11,12]. At micromolar concentrations, they inhibit ice
73 recrystallization, [13], and it is proposed they interact with the plasma membrane

74 [14,15]. Another unique property is its ability to reduce the freezing point of solutions
75 (thermal hysteresis) in a non-colligative manner, allowing this effect to be achieved
76 using significantly lower amounts compared to traditional cryoprotectants [15].

77 AF(G)Ps can vary according to their composition, structure, size, mode of
78 action, morphology of ice crystals produced and ice recrystallization inhibition (IRI)
79 activity. The present study focused on studying AFPI from Winter Flounder
80 (*Pseudopleuronectes americanus*), AFPIII from Ocean Pout (*Zoarces americanus*) and a
81 synthetic AFGP containing the native disaccharide (sequence:
82 AATdAATdAATdAATdAA).

83 AFPIs, are 3-4.5 kDa alanine-rich α -helice proteins capable to bind to the
84 pyramidal faces of ice, while AFPIIIs are small globular protein of 6.5-14 kDa that bind
85 to both, the prism plane and the pyramidal plane of ice [12,16]. AFGPs are 2.7–32 kDa
86 proteins formed of 4 to 50 tripeptide repeats of Ala–Ala–Thr with the disaccharide
87 galactose-N acetylgalactosamine attached to each Thr [12,16] and they bind to the prism
88 plane of ice crystals [17].

89 In contrast to AFPs that can be obtained by recombinant protein expression
90 techniques, the glycosylation pattern on AFGPs cannot be obtained via protein
91 expression and therefore pure samples of defined length are currently only obtained via
92 chemical synthesis [15].

93 AF(G)Ps have been used in sperm cryopreservation of different animals such as: rabbit
94 [18], buffalo [19], ram [20], miniature pig [21], sterlet [22], among others [23]
95 observing positive effects in some cases but non or detrimental effects in others. The
96 kind of effect seems to depend on various factors such as kind and concentration of
97 AF(G)P, the species, and also the cryopreservation protocol used [23].

98 Regarding chicken, a work done with AFPIII to freeze sperm from Ross 308
99 breeder-breed roosters [24] reported improved post-thawed sperm quality and fertility
100 by supplementing 1 mg/mL of the protein in the freezing media. Another study
101 conducted with White Leghorn chicken sperm, supplemented with winter wheat AFGP
102 [25], revealed an increase in fertility with frozen-thawed semen from 31- and 65-week-
103 old roosters, using 0.1 µg/mL and 1 µg/mL of the protein, respectively. These protocols
104 employed glycerol as cryoprotectant, which is known to have a contraceptive effect in
105 hen, thereby requiring its removal prior AI. In this context, the present study
106 investigated the effects of AFPI, AFP III, and AFGP on the freezability of chicken
107 sperm using DMA as cryoprotectant.

108 A previously validated cryopreservation protocol, that demonstrated improved post-
109 thaw semen quality in broiler-breeder roosters using DMA as cryoprotectant [26], was
110 taken as a base. Furthermore, the protocol was tested on a native chicken breed (Yellow
111 Hungarian), given that indigenous breeds often exhibit increased sensitivity to
112 cryoinjury and thus serve as suitable models for the optimization of semen
113 cryopreservation strategies.

114 **2. Materials and methods**

115 *2.1 Experimental Design*

116 The experimental design of the present work consisted of two parts (Fig. 1). Part 1
117 was carried out at the Centre for Genetic Resources, the Netherlands, in Wageningen
118 University and Research (WUR) and the Eindhoven University of Technology (TUE),
119 in Netherlands. This part involved the *in vitro* evaluation of AFP I, AFPIII and AFGP
120 (synthesized by the group of I. Voets, TUE) to select the best type of protein, and its

121 respective concentration, to increase the cryotolerance of chicken sperm. The range of
122 concentrations evaluated was established based on IRI activity tests (described below,
123 Fig. 2A, 2B). The freezing experiments with the different AF(G)Ps were carried out
124 with sperm of commercial broiler-breed roosters (BB) of the company Cobb (the
125 Netherlands). Part 2 involved three experiments to evaluate the effect of the selected
126 AFP on semen from the native breed Yellow Hungarian (YH), at the National Centre
127 for Biodiversity and Genetic Conservation (NBGK), Hungary. The first freezing
128 experiment was performed without AFP to compare 3 different freezing protocols and
129 select the best one for this breed. Once selected the best freezing protocol, pre-freezing
130 and freezing experiments (experiments 2 and 3) were performed to evaluate the effect of
131 supplementing AFPI in the poultry extender. Both experiments included *in vitro* tests
132 and fertility rate evaluations by artificial insemination (AI).

133 2.2 ASG-PE extender.

134 Animal Sciences Group poultry extender (ASG-PE) was used in the present work.
135 This extender contained (gram per 100 ml, mmol/l between brackets): 1.21 g (64.7)
136 sodium-L-glutamate.H₂O, 0.102 g (3.14) tri-potassium-citrate.H₂O, 0.064 g (2.97)
137 magnesium acetate.4H₂O, 0.53 g (26.5) D-(+)-glucose.H₂O, 2.43 g (114) BES (N,N-Bis
138 (2-hydroxyethyl)-2-aminoethanesulfonic acid), 0.185 g (46.2) NaOH, and Milli-Q water
139 to a final volume of 100 ml, resulting in pH 7.1 and osmolality of approximately 325
140 mOsm/kg of water [26].

141 2.3 Ice recrystallization activity of AF(G)Ps

142 For each of AF(G)Ps the IRI activity was screened in ASG-PE containing DMA
143 1.8M at TUE. These assays were performed to assess whether the components of the

144 poultry extender would affect the IRI activity of the AF(G)Ps and to identify at what
145 concentration AF(G)Ps would still induce IRI activity. Dilutions of AF(G)Ps in
146 extender containing DMA were sandwiched between two precleaned 22x22 mm cover
147 slides and rapidly cooled to -40 °C (20 °C/min), reheated to -10 °C (10 °C/min), to -8
148 °C (1 °C/min), and held at -8 °C for 30 minutes in a Linkam LTS420 stage attached to a
149 Nikon ECLIPSE Ci-Pol Optical Microscope with a Lumenera INFINITY 3 CCD
150 camera. Microphotographs were taken every minute (Figure 2A), from which ice crystal
151 areas were extracted using ImageJ and converted into average cubic radii that was
152 plotted as a function of time assuming a circular crystal shape (Figure 2B).

153 *2.4 Semen collection.*

154 Semen was collected by the abdominal massage technique [27] and was diluted 1:1
155 (v:v) directly (in the barn) after collection with ASG-PE at room temperature and
156 transported to the laboratory.

157 *2.5 Animals and semen processing*

158 *2.5.1 CGN (WUR)*

159 Semen was kindly provided by Cobb from a local research facility in the
160 Netherlands. The semen was obtained from broiler-breeder cocks at the age of 33–39
161 weeks. The samples were transported to the laboratory of CGN in approximately 30-45
162 min in a cooling box at 5 °C. Once in the laboratory, the semen samples were pooled (5
163 roosters per pool) and further processed in a refrigerated work bench set at 5 °C.
164 Motility and viability of each pool were evaluated before addition of the cryoprotectant.

165 For freezing, mother solutions of AFPI, AFPIII and AFGP were prepared at
166 concentrations of 180 µg/mL, 60 µg/mL, 60 µM, respectively with ASG-PE. From

167 these solutions the corresponding dilutions were done with ASG-PE to obtain solution
168 at concentrations of 180, 18, 6, 1.8 and 0 µg/mL of AFPI, 60, 6, 0.6, 0.06 and 0 µg/mL
169 of AFPIII and 60, 6, 0.6, 0.06 and 0 µM of AFGP. Then, 0.333 mL of these solutions,
170 pre-cooled at 5 °C, were added to 1 mL of pooled semen followed by addition of 0.666
171 ml of ASG-PE containing DMA 1.8 M and gentle mixing (final semen dilution ratio
172 **[DR]** 4x [1:3 v:v]). The final concentration of DMA was 0.6M and 30, 3, 1, 0.3 and 0
173 µg/mL of AFPI; 10, 1, 0.1, 0.01 and 0 µg/mL of AFPIII; and 10, 1, 0.1, 0.01 and 0 µM of
174 AFGP. The pools were held with DMA and the different concentrations of AF(G)P at
175 5°C for 1h, and then packed in 0.5 French straws. The straws were placed in an
176 automatic freezer (Ice Cube, 14S, Minitube, Tiefenbach, Germany) and frozen in three
177 steps: from 5 °C to -20 °C at a rate of -50 °C/min, followed by a 20-second hold at
178 -20 °C, and then continued from -20 °C to -140 °C at the same rate. This protocol
179 follows the recommendation by Woelders et al. (2022) [26] to achieve a cooling rate
180 (CR) of ≥ -50 °C/min. The frozen straws were then plunged into and maintained in
181 liquid nitrogen (at -196 °C) until thawing. For thawing, the straws were warmed for 30
182 seconds in an agitated water bath at 5 °C. Sperm quality was evaluated.

183 2.5.2 NBGK

184 Fifteen Yellow Hungarian (YH) roosters and fifteen White Leghorn (WL) roosters
185 of 1-year-old were housed under 14L:10D photoperiod and natural temperature
186 conditions in individual deep floor cages at the National Centre for Biodiversity and
187 Gene Conservation, Gödöllő, Hungary. All birds had a constant diet throughout the
188 experimental period. Specifically, the birds were fed with commercial feed containing
189 16,3 % crude protein, 10,95 AME/MJ, 3,3% crude fat, 4,2% crude fibre, 13,7 crude
190 ashes

191 *2.5.2.1 Freezing protocols without AFPI.* A first experiment was performed in absence
192 of AFP to find the best protocol for YH sperm (YH-sp). Three freezing protocols were
193 evaluated.

194 *Protocol 1.* One mL of semen was diluted with one mL of ASG-PE (DR 1:1) at
195 room temperature in the barn. The samples were transported to the laboratory in
196 approximately 10 min and placed in a cooling hood at 5 °C. After 10 min, the samples
197 were diluted for second time with 0.666 mL of ASG-PE and 1.332 mL of ASG-PE
198 containing 1.8 M of DMA (final DR 4x [1:3 v:v] and final concentration of DMA 0.6
199 M). The samples were packed in 0.5 mL straws and placed on a polystyrene rack of 2
200 cm height. The rack was then placed on the surface of liquid nitrogen inside a
201 polystyrene box with internal dimensions of 44.3 cm × 26.8 cm × 20.8 cm (L × W ×
202 H), which had been filled to a height of 6 cm (equivalent to 5.53 L) with liquid
203 nitrogen. After 10 min, the straws were plunged directly in the liquid nitrogen and
204 stored. The cooling rate achieved with this protocol was ≈ -100 °C/min) which
205 follows Woelders et al. (2022) recommendations

206 *Protocol 2* was similar to *Protocol 1* with the difference of diluting 1 mL of
207 semen with 0.5 mL of ASG-PE (DR 1:0.5, v:v) in the barn. Once in the lab and after 10
208 min of storage at 5 °C, a volume of 0.75 mL of ASG-PE containing 1.8 M of DMA was
209 added (final DR 2.3x [1:1.3 v:v], final concentration of DMA 0.6M). The diluted sperm
210 samples were kept for 1h at 5° C and frozen as in *Protocol 1*.

211 *Protocol 3.* Protocols 1 and 2 were compared with the standard method used for YH-sp
212 (*Protocol 3*). Semen was diluted with ASG-PE at room temperature in the barn (1:1,
213 v:v), taken to the lab in 10 min and placed in a cooling hood at 5 °C. After 10 min,
214 DMA (6% of the semen volume, approximately 0.65 mol/l) was added to the extended
215 semen (final DR 2.1x [1:1.1, v:v]) and the samples were maintained at 5 °C for 30

216 minutes. The samples were then packed in 0.25 mL straws. Freezing was performed
217 in two steps: first, by placing the straws 5 cm above the surface of liquid nitrogen for
218 15 minutes; then, at 1 cm above the surface for additional 15 minutes.

219 *2.5.2.2 Pre-freezing experiment with/without AFPI.* The effect of each pre-freezing step
220 on sperm quality and fertility were evaluated. These steps were: semen extension +
221 cooling (B), addition of DMA (C) or AFPI (D), and AFPI + DMA (E). Each step was
222 evaluated *in vitro* (motility, sperm abnormalities, viability, intact sperm, acrosome
223 integrity and DNA integrity) and by artificial insemination (AI). Raw pooled semen (10
224 randomly selected YH roosters / pool) was divided to evaluate steps B-E (RS for B-E).
225 Another, unprocessed pool of semen (5 randomly selected YH roosters / pool) was used
226 to evaluate the quality and fertility of raw YH-sp (step A, RS for AI). Four
227 inseminations were performed (twice a week/ two weeks) using the semen from each
228 pre-freezing step (100 million YH-sp/hen). Five groups of White Leghorn (WL) hens
229 (10 hens/group) were inseminated with: A (raw semen, RS for AI), B (raw semen
230 diluted 4x with ASG-PE and chilled for 1h at 5°C), C (B+DMA), D (B+AFPI) and E
231 (B+DMA+AFPI). Collection of eggs, started from day 2 after the first insemination
232 until day 3 after the last insemination. Fertility (% fertile/incubated eggs) of all the
233 inseminated groups was determined by candling after 7 days of incubation.

234 *2.5.2.2 Freezing experiment with/without AFPI.* Cryopreservation of semen with AFPI
235 was done as Protocol 1 with the exception of adding, in the second dilution, 0.666 mL
236 of ASG-PE containing 6 µg/mL of AFPI, (instead of ASG-PE alone). Cryopreservation
237 of YH-sp and WL-sp without AFPI were used as reference. The effect of AFPI on
238 frozen-thawed sperm was evaluated *in vitro* (motility, sperm abnormalities, viability,
239 intact sperm, acrosome integrity and DNA integrity) and by AI. Fifty hens (20 YH and

240 30 WL) were divided into 5 groups (n=10/group) and inseminated with different kind of
241 semen: (1) Raw YH-sp - WL hens; (2) F/T YH-sp - WL hens; (3) F/T YH-sp - YH
242 hens; (4) F/T YH-sp + AFPI - WL hens, (5) F/T WL semen - YH hens and (6) F/T WL
243 semen - WL hens. Semen for Groups 2, and 4 were frozen in a split-sample approach.
244 Hens were inseminated with \approx 100 million spermatozoa as follows: 3 AI/week for 2
245 weeks, and 2 AIs on the third week (8 inseminations in total). Group 1 was used to
246 know fertility of raw semen of the YH males. Comparisons (1) vs (2) assessed the effect
247 of freezing (without AFPI) on YH-sp; (2) vs (4) assessed the effect of supplementing
248 AFPI to the freezing medium; (2) vs. (3) and (5) vs (6) aimed to detect influence of the
249 female breed when using F/T semen and (3) vs (5) and (2) vs (6) aimed to detect
250 influence of the males breed when using F/T semen. Fertility was determined as
251 described in the pre-freezing experiment.

252 2.6 Assessment methods

253 *Sperm concentration and motility.* Sperm concentration was determined using an
254 Accucell (IMV, L'Aigle, France) at WUR and NBGK. Motility was assayed using a
255 computer-aided sperm analyzer system consisting on a camera (BASLER avA1000-
256 100gc, Germany[WUR] / BASLER ace U acA1300-200uc, Germany [NBGK]) coupled
257 to a phase contrast microscope (Zeis Axioscope A.1, Germany [WUR] / Nikon Eclipse
258 E200, Japan [NBGK]), and using the 12500/0000 Androvision[®] software (Minitübe,
259 Germany) [WUR] / Sperm Class Analyzer (SCA; Barcelona, Spain) v.6.0. Software
260 (Microptic S.L.) [NBGK]. For motility analysis, sperm samples were diluted to a
261 concentration of approximately 40 million sperm/mL and loaded onto glass slide at
262 room temperature (WUR) or 37 °C (NBGK). The proportion of motile spermatozoa and
263 the proportion percentage showing progressive motility were recorded. Sperm

264 kinematic variables – velocity (VCL), straight-line velocity (VSL), average path
265 velocity (VAP) – were also recorded. It has been shown that VSL and VAP are the two
266 variables most related to the ability of the sperm to reach the sperm storage tubules
267 (SSTs) at the utero-vaginal junction and subsequent fertility [28]. A minimum of 5
268 fields and 200 sperm were evaluated at a magnification of 100x for each sample.

269 *Viability* of the samples, at WUR facilities, were determined by DAPI (4',6'-
270 Diamidino-2-Phenylindole, Dihydro- chloride) diluted in ASG-PE. A sperm aliquot of
271 20 µl of semen was mixed with 20 µl of 10 µmol/L DAPI, held for 5 min at room
272 temperature in the dark, and then mixed with 10 µl of glutaraldehyde (0.5 vol%) to
273 immobilize the sperm. Two-hundred cells per sample were evaluated by epifluorescence
274 microscopy (Zeiss Axioscope A.1, Germany). The percentage of sperm cells that
275 excluded DAPI, i.e. cells with membrane integrity was determined [26]. At NBGK,
276 viability was determined using propidium iodide and SYBR-14 [29]. Two hundred cells
277 were examined under an epifluorescence microscope (Zeiss Axioskop 2 plus, Austria) at
278 40× objective (wavelength: 450–490 nm).

279 *Morphological abnormalities* (Abn) were assessed by eosin-aniline staining. The
280 eosin-aniline staining was prepared by dissolving 0.2 g of eosin and 0.8 g of aniline in
281 10 mL of Lake extender. Twenty µl of the prepared dye were pipetted into an
282 Eppendorf tube and mixed with 10 µl of semen. Ten µl of the mixture were placed
283 onto a microscope slide, spread evenly and fix the sample using a hairdryer, holding it
284 approximately 20 cm away to avoid overheating. The smears were examined under an
285 oil immersion objective at 1200× magnification (Zeiss Axioskope microscope,
286 Germany). A total of 200 sperm cells were evaluated per slide [30]. The proportion of
287 intact live sperm (ILS) was determined.

288 *Acrosome integrity* (AcI). Twenty microliters of semen were transferred to vials
289 containing 20 μ l of formaldehyde 4% in PBS for fixation. The samples were left in
290 formaldehyde for 30 min at room temperature (for non-chilled samples) and 5 °C (for
291 chilled and post-thaw samples). Ten μ L drops of the fixed samples (chilled/FT and
292 warmed) were spread onto glass slides (smears) and allowed to dry. For evaluating the
293 acrosome integrity (AcI), the smears of fixed sperm were immersed in a solution of
294 methyl blue 2.5% in PBS for 5 min, then washed with distilled water and let dry. The
295 methyl blue preparation was adapted from Santiago Moreno et al. (2009) [31]. Briefly,
296 methyl blue (Sigma-Alrich) was dissolved in PBS to a concentration of 2.5% and the
297 pH adjusted to 3.5 with acetic acid 2%. The slides were mounted and analysed under a
298 phase contrast microscope (Zeiss Axioskop 2 plus, camera Micro Publisher 6, Canada)
299 at 1000 \times magnification. Sperm with abnormal morphology of the acrosome (hooks,
300 swollen, thinned or absence) were considered lacking in acrosome integrity [31]; 200
301 cells were examined.

302 *DNA integrity* was assessed as described by Bernal et al. (2021) [32] and the
303 samples analysed under a fluorescent microscope (Zeiss Axioskop 2 plus, camera
304 Micro Publisher 6, Canada). Percentages of positive TUNEL spermatozoa per sample
305 were recorded by counting a minimum of 200 spermatozoa per microscopy preparation.

306 *2.7 Identification of very early (oviductal) embryo death*

307 After the eggs were cracked, yolks were carefully separated from the albumen and
308 placed into a 0.9% NaCl solution. Germinal discs that appeared infertile were gently
309 removed from the vitelline membrane, immersed in 0.9% NaCl, and stained on
310 microscope slides with propidium iodide (PI). The working solution contained 5 μ g PI
311 per ml of 0.9% NaCl, from which 5 μ l was applied to each slide. The presence of cell

312 nuclei, serving as an indicator of fertility (Fig. 3), was assessed using a fluorescence
313 microscope (Leitz-Dioplan) at 500× magnification [33].

314 *2.8 Statistical analysis*

315 Data are presented as means ± SEM. Proportional variables were transformed using
316 the arcsine square root transformation. Residual normality was confirmed using
317 histograms of raw residuals, plots of residuals vs normal expected value (Q-Q), and
318 plots of residual vs predicted values.

319 Individual general linear models (GLMs) were fitted for each variable. Treatment
320 and semen group were categorical fixed factors. Type III sums of squares were applied
321 to models with empty cells. To correct for multiple testing, p-values were adjusted using
322 the Benjamini-Hochberg FDR (False Discovery Rate) procedure. Post-hoc of Tukey or
323 Tukey-Kramer (for variables with empty cells) were applied to variables showing
324 significant differences.

325 Results from YH and WL frozen sperm were analyzed by 2×2 factorial design (YH
326 and WL × fresh and F/T) to evaluate the interaction between breed and treatment for
327 each variable. Due to missing data in some variables, individual factorial analyses were
328 conducted per variable. No significant breed × treatment interactions were found ($p >$
329 0.05), so main effects were analyzed independently. P-values from the factorial and the
330 main effects analysis were adjusted using FDR method to account for multiple testing.

331 Fertility results were analyzed to compare the treatments using Pearson Chi-square
332 tests and FDR adjustments, with a significance set at $\alpha = 0.05$ for 10 combinations (Fig.
333 4), 15 combinations (Figure 5A) and 4 combinations (Figure 5B).

334 All statistical analyses were conducted using TIBCO Statistica™ software, version
335 13.3 (TIBCO® Software Inc., Palo Alto, CA, USA). Differences were considered
336 statistically significant at $P < 0.05$.

337 **3. RESULTS**

338 Figure 2A illustrates the ability of AF(G)Ps to inhibit ice recrystallization over
339 time, despite being diluted in the poultry extender containing DMA. Smaller ice crystal
340 radii were observed with increasing protein concentrations (Fig. 2A and B). As shown
341 in figures 2A and B, all concentrations of AF(G)Ps tested in the present study exhibited
342 IRI activity.

343 Freezing of BB sperm revealed no significant differences when supplementing
344 AFGP to the freezing medium. In the case of AFPIII, statistical analysis revealed
345 significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in total motility (TM) and progressive motility (PM)
346 between the control group and all treatments containing AFPIII. However, these
347 differences were not visually evident when comparing the group means (Table 1).

348 The presence of AFPI increased the viability at concentrations of 0.3 and 3 $\mu\text{g/mL}$
349 ($P=0.007$ and 0.009 , respectively) (Table 1) while 1 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ increased TM ($P=0.03$), PM
350 ($P=0.034$) and VCL ($P=0.024$).

351 The results obtained from the three freezing protocols for YH-sp (Table 2) showed
352 significant differences ($P < 0.05$) regarding viability, ILS, and Abn. Protocol 1 gave the
353 highest viability compared to protocol 3 ($P=0.0002$) and % of ILS compared to Protocol
354 2 ($P=0.0002$). Protocol 3 gave the lowest Abn ($P=0.0013$) compared with Protocol 2.
355 Considering these results, Protocol 1 was selected as the best protocol to test AFPI. The
356 low sperm concentration resulting from the 4x sperm dilution (≈ 100 million sperm/mL)

357 required an increased number of artificial inseminations from 4 to 8 to adequately assess
358 the fertility of the frozen/thawed (F/T) samples.

359 Sperm samples for AI of the pre-freezing experiment (groups A-E) were
360 characterized before insemination. The results (Table 3) showed higher values for PM,
361 VCL, VSL, VAP in semen of Groups B (P=0.002, 0.002, 0.0003 and 0.0002,
362 respectively) and D (P= 0.02, 0.02, 0.03, 0.01, respectively) compared with Group A.
363 Additionally semen of Group B also had higher TM than Group A (P=0.03).
364 Comparisons were also made between treatments B–E and the original pool of RS from
365 which they were derived (RS for B-E). The results (Table 3) showed a significant
366 decrease in ILS in semen of Group C (semen containing DMA alone) compared to RS
367 for B-E (P=0.02), while the Abn values increased in Groups B (P=0.03), C (P=0.0004)
368 and E (P=0.001). Semen groups C and E (both containing DMA) also showed the
369 lowest values for PM, VSL, and VAP, differing significantly ($p<0.05$) from Group B,
370 which presented the highest values. Semen of Group C displayed the lowest TM value,
371 significantly lower than those of groups B (P=0.02) and D (P=0.04). No significant
372 differences were observed in viability, VCL, acrosome integrity or DNA integrity
373 among groups.

374 AI with treatments A-E revealed significant differences among the groups. Group A
375 showed the highest fertility and had significant differences (P<0.01) with all groups
376 except with Group C (P=0.1). Unexpectedly, a marked decrease in fertility (P=0.0000)
377 was observed (Fig. 4) in Group B (chilled semen in ASG-PE) compared to Group A
378 while Groups C, D, and E exhibited higher fertility rates (P=0.0000, 0.002, 0.002,
379 respectively) than Group B.

380 Characterization of F/T sperm from YH and WL before AI (Table 4) showed no
381 interaction between freezability and rooster breed. DNA integrity was the only variable
382 affected ($P=0.0004$) by rooster breed, with WL semen showing more DNA
383 cryoresistance. The treatment (fresh vs. frozen) resulted in significantly lower values for
384 the frozen/thawed (F/T) samples across all variables, except for VCL ($P=0.054$).
385 Regarding YH-sp samples frozen with or without AFPI (Table 5), no appreciable effect
386 of AFPI supplementation was seen compared to the non-supplemented samples, except
387 for DNA integrity, which was significantly increased ($P=0.004$) in the presence of
388 AFPI.

389 The results obtained from artificial insemination (AI) with F/T sperm are shown in
390 Figure 5A. No fertility was observed in Groups 2 and 3. Group 4, which received AFPI,
391 achieved a fertility rate of 1.5%, though this was not significantly different from the
392 other groups. Groups 5 and 6, inseminated with frozen/thawed (F/T) sperm from White
393 Leghorn (WL) roosters, showed fertility rates of 3.4% and 3.9%, respectively. No
394 significant differences were observed with respect to the breed of hen.

395 Closer inspection of the eggs initially classified as unfertile during candling
396 revealed that approximately 18% had been fertilized (Fig. 5A), but the embryos had
397 died at very early stage, likely within the oviduct.

398 Analysis of the fertility rate per week (Fig. 5B) of raw semen (Group 1) showed
399 that the maximum fertility rate could not be maintained in the 3rd week, when the
400 number of inseminations was decreased to 2 per week.

401 **4. DISCUSSION**

402 Comparisons among the different AF(G)Ps revealed that AFPI exhibited a superior
403 protective effect compared to AFPIII and AFGP, despite all tested concentrations of
404 these proteins exhibiting IRI activity. In this respect, research has demonstrated that
405 performance of individual AF(G)Ps may vary depending on factors such as their
406 adsorption rate, cooling rate or the degree of supercooling experienced [13]. Moreover,
407 studies using model membranes with varying lipid types demonstrated that AFPI and
408 AFGP interactions are lipid-specific, indicating that the protective efficacy of these
409 proteins is influenced by the composition of the lipid bilayer [34,35].

410 For the YH semen, we evaluated both the DR 4× used with BB-sp and DR 2.3×.
411 These treatments were further compared to a standard freezing protocol for YH semen,
412 which employs a DR of 2.1×. The results showed that the DR 4× yielded the highest
413 viability. The beneficial effect of higher DRs compared to lower ones have been also
414 reported in other studies [2,36]. A possible explanation could be the dilution of harmful
415 substances present in raw semen [5,37,38], and/or the presence of beneficial
416 components in the diluent—excluding DMA, as all three DRs used the same final DMA
417 concentration 0.6 mol/L.

418 Sperm characterization of the 5 pre-freezing steps (groups A-E) showed that chilled
419 sperm with DMA had lower values in most of the motility parameters (except TM)
420 compared to ASG-PE alone, which yielded the highest motility—even higher than the
421 “RS for AI” group. Based on these results, better fertility was expected with semen
422 chilled in ASG-PE and poorer outcomes with the semen chilled in presence of DMA.
423 However, fertility decreased in all groups compared to the “RS for AI” group.
424 Surprisingly, adding DMA to ASG-PE strongly mitigated this decline, eliminating the
425 significant differences in fertility compared with the “RS for AI” group.

426 AFPI alone prevented significantly the increase in sperm abnormalities, in contrast
427 to DMA and DMA-AFPI treatments, which showed the highest abnormality rates.
428 Despite this significant difference, AFPI and DMA-AFPI exhibited similar fertility
429 rates. AFPI and AFPI-DMA treatments also showed reduced fertility versus the “RS for
430 AI” group, but their fertility rates remained significantly superior to that of ASG-PE
431 alone

432 Among the possible causes that explain the loss of fertility observed with chilled
433 sperm in ASG-PE we could find, a detrimental effect of the ASG-PE itself, or damage
434 induced by cooling/chilling that was not detected by the evaluated parameters. The first
435 hypothesis was discarded based on findings from a separate study (not part of this
436 work), in which insemination with ASG-PE treated sperm, but not subjected to chilling,
437 resulted in higher fertility rates than chilled semen [39] which points chilling injury as a
438 possible cause of fertility loss.

439 No serious changes in sperm motility, viability or acrosome integrity were found
440 across treatments A-E, however the serious impact of chilling on the fertility was
441 evident after AI. This could be related to damages induced by rewarming [40] of the
442 chilled sperm inside the hen or to damages that are only evident after rewarming.

443 A similar loss of chicken sperm fertility after chilling in absence of cryoprotectant,
444 was previously reported by Elomda et al., (2024) [41]; however, the impact on fertility
445 was less pronounced (18.2%), which coincided, in their study, with the presence of
446 polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) in the chicken extender. PVP has been hypothesized to
447 exert cryoprotective effects through colligative properties, by coating cell membranes
448 [42] or by inhibiting freezing-induced protein dissociation [43]. Thus, supplementing

449 protective macromolecules in the poultry extender may perhaps prevent the loss of
450 fertility during cooling/chilling.

451 The loss of fertility observed during chilling was significant mitigated by the
452 presence of DMA or AFPI, observing the highest protection role for the former. The
453 protective role of internal cryoprotectants as DMA is attributed to their capacity to
454 maintain the fluidity of the sperm membranes at low temperatures [44] by decreasing
455 the lipid phase transition temperature of the cell membranes. Regarding AFPI, several
456 works have reported a stabilizing effect of AF(G)Ps of the cell membranes [34,45].
457 There was no additional gain by using the AFPI-DMA combination.

458 Artificial insemination with F/T sperm of YH gave zero fertility in absence of the
459 AFPI, independently of the breed of hen, and some very low fertility in the presence of
460 the protein. Inseminations with RS ruled out infertility in the YH roosters. However, it
461 is worth noting that, after four inseminations with RS in the current batch of hens, the
462 fertility rate was only about 50%, suggesting limited reproductive performance within
463 this group.

464 The fertility rates obtained with F/T sperm could suggest that the freezing protocol
465 failed to preserve the functionality of the sperm. However, the analysis on embryo dead
466 in the fertility assays with F/T sperm indicated that a percentage of sperm, from YH and
467 WL roosters, were able to fertilize the eggs but the embryos were not able to continue
468 developing. This observation could be a consequence of inseminating an insufficient
469 number of spermatozoa, caused by the low concentration of semen doses. According to
470 Hemmings and Birkhead (2015) [46], when very few sperm penetrate the avian ovum,
471 embryos are unlikely to survive beyond the earliest stages of development. The inability
472 to maintain fertility over time with raw semen doses may reflect limited sperm storage

473 in the sperm storage tubules (SSTs) compromising the embryo development. On this
474 basis, the observation that hens (YH and WL) inseminated with WL sperm showed
475 higher fertility rates (though not statistically significant) compared to those inseminated
476 with YH sperm could be attributed to the higher sperm dose of the WL group which
477 contained approximately 1.8 times more spermatozoa. However, the higher DNA
478 cryoresistance observed in WL sperm may have also contributed to these results.

479 In conclusion, cryopreservation of semen could be an instrument in conserving rare
480 breeds, but freezing and thawing of YH semen is still a challenge.

481 This study showed that pre-freeze processing steps such as extending-cooling, can
482 already strongly reduce the fertility of the semen, albeit, this reduction was lower in the
483 presence of DMA and/or AFPI. Future studies may address why the pre-freeze fertility
484 was lowered and how it can be prevented, e.g. by using protective macromolecules
485 already during cooling, and/or by more gradual cooling.

486 With the current freezing protocol and insemination dose, the fertility of
487 frozen/thawed (F/T) semen was very low. Given that sperm concentration in raw YH
488 semen is also relatively low, it becomes necessary to increase the sperm dose without
489 compromising post-thaw sperm quality.

490 AFPI had a small but significant positive effect on some post-thaw sperm
491 variables. It is yet unclear whether AFPI may also affect fertility of F/T semen, albeit
492 that the only fertile eggs obtained with F/T YH semen were obtained using AFPI. It
493 may be necessary to change pre-freeze semen processing to avoid pre-freeze loss of
494 fertility and to yield sufficiently concentrated insemination sperm dosages.

495

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501 **DECLARATION OF COMPETING INTERESTS**

502 None.

503 **DECLARATION OF GENERATIVE AI AND AI-ASSISTED TECHNOLOGIES**
504 **IN THE WRITING PROCESS**

505 During the preparation of this work the author(s) used ChatGPT in order to improve
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Table 1. Rooster sperm variables of thawed semen of broiler-breeder roosters, from Netherlands frozen in presence of different anti-freeze (glycol)proteins.

	AFPI (µg/mL)				
	0	0.3	1	3	30
Viability(%)	50.2±1.1 ^{bc}	56.1±1.5 ^a	54.6±1.6 ^{ab}	56.0±1.3 ^a	46.3±1.1 ^c
TM (%)	25.9±1.0 ^{bc}	28.4±1.2 ^{ab}	29.7±1.1 ^a	28.8±1.9 ^{ab}	22.9±1.2 ^c
PM (%)	20.6±1.0 ^{bc}	22.9±1.3 ^{ab}	24.1±1.1 ^a	23.4±1.7 ^{ab}	17.7±1.2 ^c
VCL(µm/s)	56.3±1.6 ^a	59.4±1.3 ^{ab}	60.2±1.8 ^a	58.6±1.6 ^{ab}	55.9±1.9 ^b
VSL(µm/s)	38.9±1.2	40.1±4.7	40.1±1.4	39.1±1.4	39.9±1.8
VAP(µm/s)	43.6±1.3	45.1±1.0	45.4±1.4	44.1±1.3	44.3±1.8
	AFPIII (µg/mL)				
	0	0.01	0.1	1	10
Viability(%)	51.8±1.1	54.6±1.1	55.2±0.7	54.9±0.6	54.1±1.3
TM (%)	27.1±1.2 ^b	26.6±1.5 ^a	27.5±1.1 ^a	27.1±1.6 ^a	27.8±1.3 ^a
PM (%)	21.6±1.1 ^b	21.4±1.2 ^a	22.2±1.2 ^a	21.8±1.5 ^a	22.1±1.1 ^a
VCL(µm/s)	57.1±1.7	59.3±1.9	58.1±1.8	58.7±2.3	58.3±1.5
VSL(µm/s)	39.7±1.4	40.7±1.5	39.9±1.0	40.7±2.0	39.2±0.8
VAP(µm/s)	44.7±1.4	45.7±1.6	44.7±1.1	45.6±1.9	44.3±0.9
	AFGP (nM)				
	0	0.01	0.1	1	10
Viability(%)	49.7±1.8	51.9±1.6	54.6±1.7	52.3±1.8	49.8±2.5
TM (%)	25.3±1.3	27.8±1.8	26.2±1.3	27.9±1.3	26.1±1.7
PM (%)	19.9±1.3	22.5±1.8	20.9±1.2	22.5±1.4	20.2±1.5
VCL(µm/s)	57.2±1.5	59.5±1.9	57.6±1.2	59.4±1.1	55.8±1.3
VSL(µm/s)	38.9±0.9	40.3±1.1	39.9±1.0	41.0±1.1	38.8±1.0
VAP(µm/s)	43.6±0.9	45.4±1.1	44.7±0.9	46.0±1.2	43.4±1.0

*Significant differences among some of the pools. Abbreviations: TM, total motile, PM,

progressive motile; VCL: curvilinear velocity, VSL: straight-line velocity, VAP: average path velocity; AFPI, anti-freeze protein I, AFP III anti-freeze protein III, AFGP, Anti-freeze glycoprotein. Means within a row with no common superscript differ significantly (P< 0.05).

Table 2. Rooster sperm variables of fresh and frozen-thawed semen of Yellow Hungarian roosters using three different cryopreservation methods

	Fresh	Freezing Method		
		1	2	3
Viability (%) [*]	92.9±0.9 ^a	56.7±3.0 ^b	49.0±3.4 ^{bc}	42.8±4.7 ^c
ILS (%) [*]	82.3±0.9 ^a	34.5±3.0 ^b	27.7±1.4 ^c	29.7±1.6 ^{bc}
Abn (%) [*]	10.7±0.9 ^c	15.5±1.0 ^{ab}	19.1±1.6 ^a	12.0±1.4 ^{bc}
TM (%) [*]	65.5±5.4 ^a	27.3±3.4 ^b	26.3±1.8 ^b	21.0±2.7 ^b
PM (%)	41.0±7.0 ^a	15.3±3.1 ^b	15.3±1.7 ^b	11.5±2.1 ^b
VCL(µm/s) [*]	68.8±6.1 ^a	51.2±2.0 ^b	50.0±4.9 ^b	46.6±2.2 ^b
VSL(µm/s)	44.8±5.0 ^a	28.1±2.1 ^b	27.8±2.8 ^b	24.1±2.2 ^b
VAP(µm/s)	31.7±3.8 ^a	18.6±2.0 ^b	18.4±1.9 ^b	15.8±2.1 ^b
AcI(%)	87.9±1.6 ^a	73.1±4.2 ^b	73.1±4.5 ^b	70.3±5.8 ^b
DNA fragmentation (%)	ND	39.2±4.8	45.6±3.3	49.8±3.3

^{*}Significant differences among some of the pools. Abbreviations: ILS, intact live sperm;

Abn, abnormalities, TM, total motile, PM, progressive motile, VCL, curvilinear velocity;

VSL, straight-line velocity; VAP, average path velocity; AcI, acrosome integrity; ND,

not determined. Means within a row with no common superscript differ significantly (P< 0.05).

Table 3. Yellow Hungarian sperm variables of: raw semen used for artificial insemination (A, RS for AI), raw semen aliquoted to prepare treatments B, C, D and E (Raw semen for B-E), cooled extended semen (B), cooled extended semen containing DMA(C), cooled extended semen containing AFPI (D), cooled extended semen containing DMA+AFPI (E). Semen of groups A, B, C, D and E were inseminated (100 million sperm) to White Leghorn hens.

	A (RS for AI)	RS for B-E	B (ASG-PE, 5°C, 1h)	C (B+DMA)	D (B+AFPI)	E (B+DMA+AF PI)
Viability (%)	85.5±3.8	93.4±1.1	87.5±2.9	90.4±1.6	86.7±2.1	89.1±2.4
Intact live sperm (%)	81.0±1.2	85.7±1.1 ^a	81.4±3.5 ^{ab}	75.8±2.6 ^b	81.6±2.0 ^{ab}	77.9±3.7 ^{ab}
Abnormalities (%)	14.1 ±1.7	7.8±1.3 ^c	13.6±2.8 ^{ab}	18.8±2.0 ^a	12.1±2.2 ^{bc}	18.3±3.4 ^a
Total motility (%)	47.7±12.4 ^{BC}	68.4±10.2 ^{ab}	80.0±3.4 ^{a, A}	43.3±6.3 ^{b, C}	77.4±3.5 ^{a, AB}	51.2±4.4 ^{ab, ABC}
Progressive motility (%)	19.8±7.3 ^C	42.9±15.8 ^{ab}	67.9±6.7 ^{a, A}	27.1±6.2 ^{b, BC}	55.3±7.5 ^{ab, AB}	23.9±2.3 ^{b, C}
VCL(µm/s)	55.7±5.9 ^C	81.7±21.6	105.7±5.1 ^A	61.7±11.5 ^C	93.5±13.3 ^{AB}	72.2±13.0 ^{BC}
VSL(µm/s)	20.7±2.4 ^C	37.3±10.6 ^{ab}	60.7±2.4 ^{a, A}	24.1±2.3 ^{b, BC}	40.9±5.2 ^{ab, B}	27.4±4.9 ^{b, BC}
VAP(µm/s)	29.7±2.6 ^C	51.6±14.9 ^{ab}	77.4±2.5 ^{a, A}	35.2±4.0 ^{b, C}	58.0±6.1 ^{ab, AB}	40.7±6.7 ^{b, BC}
Acrosome integrity (%)	86.8±5.5	89.3±2.6	83.5±6.6	86.9±2.6	84.1±4.1	77.6±6.1
DNA integrity (%)	98.1±1.5	96.2±1.7	98.7±1.2	97.8±0.8	97.2±2.6	98.4±0.7

Different uppercase superscripts indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$) among “RS for AI” (A) and groups B, C, D and E. Different lowercase superscripts indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$) among “RS for B-E” and groups B, C, D and E.

Table 4. Rooster sperm variables of fresh and frozen-thawed semen of Yellow Hungarian and White Leghorn roosters frozen with DMA

	Breed		Treatment		Breed×Treatment				Significance		
	YH	WL	Fresh	Frozen	YH		WL		Breed	Treatment	Breed×treatment
					Fresh	Frozen	Fresh	Frozen			
Viability (%)	70.3±5.1	68.9±5.3	91.2±1.3 ^a	47.0±1.7 ^b	92.3±1.1	48.4±1.9	90.6±2.1	45.3±3.0	NS	*	NS
ILS (%)	59.1±6.4	58.7±7.2	87.7±0.7 ^a	29.2±1.6 ^b	86.4±1.0	31.8±2.2	89.6±0.7	27.8±1.8	NS	*	NS
Abn (%)	13.5±1.5	12.4±1.7	8.0±0.6 ^a	18.4±1.5 ^b	8.9 ±0.7	18.2±2.0	6.7±0.8	18.1±2.0	NS	*	NS
TM (%)	44.7±3.1	55.4±4.4	60.8±4.0 ^a	39.8±2.1 ^b	52.2±4.4	37.2±3.0	70.7±4.4	40.1±2.9	NS	*	NS
PM (%)	29.5±2.7	39.5±4.4	42.1±4.2 ^a	28.0±2.6 ^b	33.6±3.5	25.3±3.8	51.8±5.7	27.2±3.9	NS	*	NS
VCL(μm/s)	62.6±3.9	69.2±5.3	68.3±4.7	60.2±3.5	64.3±6.3	60.7±4.8	80.9±7.9	57.4±5.3	NS	NS	NS
VSL(μm/s)	29.3±2.2	33.1±3.6	36.2±3.0 ^a	25.5±2.0 ^b	32.7±2.8	25.6±3.0	42.4±4.8	23.8±2.9	NS	*	NS
VAP(μm/s)	40.6±2.9	45.6±4.4	48.4±4.0 ^a	36.5±2.6 ^b	44.0±4.1	36.8±3.9	56.7±6.3	34.4±3.7	NS	*	NS
AcI (%)	90.2±3.4	94.4±2.0	96.6±0.5 ^a	91.4±2.2 ^b	96.0±0.8	84.4±7.5	97.5±0.6	91.4±3.7	NS	*	NS
DNA integrity (%)	71.0±5.6 ^b	81.7±5.0 ^a	95.7±1.3 ^a	57.1±3.7 ^b	92.3±1.9	49.8±4.0	99.1±0.3	64.4±5.5	*	*	NS

Abbreviations: * significant (p<0.05); YH, Yellow Hungarian; WL, White Leghorn; NS, not significant; ILS, intact live sperm; Abn, abnormalities, TM, total motile, PM, progressive motile, VCL, curvilinear velocity; VSL, straight-line velocity; VAP, average path velocity; AcI, acrosome integrity; ND, not determined; YH, Yellow Hungarian; DMA, dimethylacetamide. Different superscripts within a row differ significantly (p≤ 0.05).

Table 5. Rooster sperm variables of fresh and frozen-thawed semen of Yellow Hungarian frozen with DMA, in presence or absence of AFPI

	Fresh	Frozen without AFPI	Frozen with AFPI
Viability (%)	92.3±1.1 _a	48.4±1.9 ^b	51.0±1.1 ^b
Intact live sperm (%)	86.4±1.0 _a	31.8±2.2 ^b	35.1±2.7 ^b
Abnormalities (%)	8.9±0.7 ^a	18.2±2.0 ^b	17.5±2.3 ^b
Total motility (%)	52.2±4.4 _a	37.2±3.0 ^b	35.0±1.9 ^b
Progressive motility (%)	33.6±3.5	25.3±3.8	24.9±2.9
VCL(μm/s)	64.3±6.3	60.7±4.8	61.0±5.9
VSL(μm/s)	32.7±2.8	25.6±3.0	24.0±2.3
VAP(μm/s)	44.0±4.1	36.8±3.9	35.5±3.3
Acrosome integrity (%)	96.0±0.8	84.4±7.5	86.9±5.0
DNA integrity (%)	92.3±1.9 _a	49.8±4.0 ^c	70.2±4.6 ^b

Abbreviations: AFPI, antifreeze protein I; VCL, curvilinear velocity; VSL, straight-line velocity; VAP, average path velocity. Different superscripts within a row differ significantly (p< 0.05).

Fig. 1. Experimental Design. AFPI, antifreeze protein I; AFPIII, antifreeze protein III; AFGP, antifreeze glycoprotein; IRI, ice recrystallization inhibition; BB, broiler-breed; TUE, Eindhoven University of Technology; WUR, Wageningen University and Research; NBGK, National Centre for Biodiversity and Gene Conservation (Hungary); w/o, without; YH, Yellow Hungarian; WL, White Leghorn; DMA, dimethylacetamide; AI, artificial insemination.

Fig. 2A. Microphotographs of ice recrystallization activity assay for extender + 1.8 mol/l of DMA (top, 0 ug/mL), and dilutions of AFP III (0.3, 3 and 30 ug/mL), AFP I (0.3 and 30 ug/mL) and AFGP (0.001, 0.1, 10 μ M).

Fig. 2B. Average cubic radio of ice crystals in extender + DMA 1.8 mol/l over time, in the presence of AFP III, AFP I and AFGP at different concentrations.

Fig. 3. Identification of very early (oviductal) embryo death. Germinal discs were gently removed from the vitelline membrane, immersed in 0.96 % NaCl and stained on microscope slides with propidium iodide. The presence of cell nuclei is an indicator of fertility. Unfertile germinal disc (left) and fertile germinal disc (right). (Photographs taken by Dr. Krisztina Liptó, NBGK)

Fig. 4. Fertility rates obtained using fresh (not frozen) YH-sp to inseminate WL hens. (A) neat semen; (B) neat semen extended 1:3 in ASG and chilled for 1h at 5°C, C (B+DMA), D (B+AFPI) and E (B+DMA+AFPI). Abbreviations: sp, sperm; YH-sp, Yellow Hungarian sperm, WL, White Leghorn, DMA, dimethylacetamide; AFPI, antifreeze protein I. Different letters on bars represent significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in fertility rate among the groups

Fig. 5A. Black bars: fertility rate obtained from artificial inseminations using raw semen (Group 1) or frozen-thawed sperm (F/T-sp, Groups 2-6) of Yellow Hungarian (YH, Groups 1-4) and White Leghorn (WL, Groups 5-6) roosters (♂) inseminated in YH (Groups 3 and 5) and WL (Groups 1, 2, 4 and 6) hens (♀). Groups 1-6 corresponds to different combinations of breed and sex: (1) YH-sp raw semen- WL hen; (2) F/T YH-sp - WL hen; (3) F/T YH-sp - YH hen; (4) F/T YH-sp + AFPI - WL hen; (5) F/T WL-sp - YH hen; (6), F/T WL-sp - WL hen. Semen samples used in groups 2-6 were frozen with DMA 0.6 M, but group 4 was additionally supplemented with AFPI (1µg/mL). Grey bars: very early (oviductal) embryonic death identified in eggs initially deemed infertile by candling but later confirmed as fertile through PI staining. **5B.** Fertility rate per week of Group 1. Abbreviations: DMA, dimethylacetamide; AFPI, anti-freeze protein I. Different letters on bars represent significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in fertility rate among the groups or weeks.

Experimental Design

AFPI, AFP III, AFGP

AFPI
(NBGK)

IRI tests
(TUE)

Freezing BB semen
(WUR)

Compare protocols 1,2,3
(w/o AFPI)

Protocol 1

Pre-freezing experiment
YH semen

Freezing experiment
YH, WL semen,

Effect of
RS, extending+cooling, DMA, AFPI, AFPI+ DMA
(Groups A, B, C, D, E)

Addition of
DMA, AFPI + DMA
(only DMA for WL semen)

In vitro

Fertility rates
(AI)

In vitro

Fertility rates
(AI)

WL hens

YH hens

WL hens

AFP III

Zoom: AFP III

AFP I

Zoom: AFP I

AFGP

Zoom: AFGP

Total millions
sp inseminated: 581

580

A

B